

Degree of Optimism towards Team Effectiveness Skill of the Grade 12 Accountancy, Business, and Management Students

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Abstract

Individuals who exhibit an optimistic mindset have good entrepreneurial skills in terms of team effectiveness. Optimism refers to the individual's positive outlook on life that may influence their personality and behavior which involve life skills and competencies. In entrepreneurship, team effectiveness is an essential entrepreneurial skill that may affect the outcome of work productivity. This study aims to determine if optimism relates to skills and competencies. It specifically assesses whether the optimism level of an individual correlates with their level of team effectiveness skill. The study employed a quantitative research method, particularly descriptive-correlational. In order to assess the hypothesis that optimism level relates to the level of team effectiveness skill, an online survey questionnaire was disseminated to students of Lourdes College, Inc. located in Cagayan de Oro City. Participants were purposely sampled such that respondents were only taken from the Grade 12 Accountancy, Business, and Management students. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive, and inferential statistics utilizing the mean and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation, respectively. The results showed a positive relationship between the optimism and team effectiveness skill of the participants, and significant p values in favor of the alternative hypothesis. These findings suggest that individuals who have higher optimism are more entrepreneurially skilled in terms of team effectiveness. With this premise, the development of individual optimism should be taken into consideration when developing team effectiveness skill.

Keywords: Optimism. Entrepreneurial skill. Team effectiveness. ABM.

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Introduction

An individual with an optimistic mindset exhibits good entrepreneurial skill in terms of team effectiveness (Achor & Gelan, 2020). Optimism is the belief that situations will turn out good (Carver et al., 2014; Atalaya, 2012; Reivich, 2013). In the field of entrepreneurship, optimism has been observed to be an undervalued trait due to the lack of literature, as well as studies, that assess the relationship between optimism and team effectiveness skill (Beheshtifar, 2013, as cited in Madar et al., 2019; Kenneally, 2015). Optimism is an underrated trait that can enhance and develop one's entrepreneurial intelligence quotient (Ashworth-Keppel, 2018).

Team Effectiveness is the capability of a team to obtain objectives and goals (Cooke & Hilton, 2015, as cited in Rico et al., 2011). It has eight known aspects: Purpose and Goals, Roles, Team Processes, Team Relationships, Intergroup Relations, Problem Solving, Passion and Commitment, and Skills and Learning (London Leadership Academy, n.d.). A successful entrepreneur has strong leadership qualities referring to the strong communication skills and the ability to encourage people to achieve a common goal and work effectively, i.e., an entrepreneur should be team effective (Bowser, 2010). A study in Manila also found that Filipino workers highly rates positive attitude as a trait that should be embodied by aspiring entrepreneurs (Alafriz et al., 2014).

Jeraj (2014) regards optimism as an attribute that governs positive thinking and outlook of the future which may lead to better performance, well-being, and coping strategies. In the LinkedIn Opportunity Index 2020 (Cahiles-Magkilat, 2020), Filipinos are considered to be optimistic workers and it was further stated that although the younger generations are more optimistic when engaging in opportunities, it was uncertain for the Filipino youth. Additionally, Wiseman (2013) negates the idea that optimism is useful because of the lacking sense of reality and the belief of an illusion wherein everything will have a good outcome.

It has been observed by the researchers, who are also students of Lourdes College, Inc., that the Grade 12 Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) students are having difficulty in maintaining a positive outlook such that, as presented through monthly sessions with their respective advisers, they are exhausted in doing school works while some are having doubts about their chosen course. On the other hand, the team effectiveness of the students were also affected in the sense that the online classes are not that much effective. This can be supported by peer evaluations from major subjects of the course wherein the students have stated that it is difficult to work in a group because some members are inactive or non-participative, while there are some who find it hard to work together with the group because of the lack of communication and interaction.

With that, the study aims to determine the optimism level of the Grade 12 Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) students and its relationship towards their team effectiveness skill. The main purpose is to give knowledge to the society about the correlation between optimism and entrepreneurial skills which can aid in understanding the value of optimism as well as its influence regarding team effectiveness skill.

The present study's main focus is determining a relationship between optimism and team effectiveness skill of the Grade 12 ABM students in a private institution in Cagayan de Oro City. Primarily, the study sought to 1) determine the degree of optimism of the participants; 2) determine the level of entrepreneurial skill of the respondents in terms of team effectiveness and its aspects; and 3) test if there is a significant relationship between the respondents' degree of optimism towards their team effectiveness skill as well as its aspects. Since the research questions include the overall team effectiveness skill and its eight aspects, the researchers have identified nine null hypotheses which state that there is no significant relationship between the participants' level of optimism towards their team effectiveness skill, including its eight aspects.

Methods

The study made use of the quantitative type of research specifically descriptive-correlational which involves the structured investigation on the nature of interconnection between variables, independent and dependent, rather than direct cause-effect relationships (Sousa et al., 2007). The method is suitable such that the research only aims to determine a relationship between the variables without acknowledging the possible cause and effects.

The research instrument utilized in the study was composed of two separate survey questionnaires. The first questionnaire was adopted from Carver et al. (1994). It is well-known as the Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R) which comprises of questions following a direct and reverse scoring pattern. The second questionnaire was also fully adopted from the London Leadership Academy (n.d.) which consisted of 56 questions wherein the eight (8) aspects were given seven (7) items each. Both questionnaires utilized a 5-point Likert scale.

The population of the study involved the entire Senior High School (SHS) students of Lourdes College, Inc. located in Cagayan de Oro City. Purposive sampling was used as the research will only highlight a part of the population (Palinkas et al., 2016). This means that the sample would only be coming from the Grade 12 ABM strand since they are most likely to engage in entrepreneurship or entrepreneurial activities relevant to their course. The current population size of the entire SHS department was 1,243 students so with that, a sample size determiner was utilized in order to calculate the sample size suitable for the study. With a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 8%, the determined sample size was 134.

In gathering the data, since there is the occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic, the procedures were done online. The researchers, first, had to present a consent letter to the SHS Coordinator, ABM Strand Coordinator, and all the advisers under the strand, in order to gain permission in conducting the online survey. After approved, the researchers asked the strand advisers to provide a list of the students currently enrolled in their class for the selection of participants. Once the participants were listed, the researchers gave them a permission letter to determine if they are willing to participate. Respondents were given a right to refuse to participate in the survey. Once accepted, the Google Form link containing the questionnaire was given to the respondents. Screenshots after submission were required in order to fully acknowledge the participant's involvement in the study.

The study utilized two statistical methods. The first and second research questions were treated with a descriptive statistical method, specifically the mean. Meanwhile, the third research question was treated with an inferential statistical tool, Spearman Rank-Order Correlation. In testing the significance of the Spearman Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho), post hoc t-tests for correlation were utilized in order to determine the p value while the level of significance (α) is at 0.05, the alternative hypothesis being that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' optimism level and level of team effectiveness skill, including the eight aspects.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What is the degree of optimism of the participants?

Figure 1 Overall Distribution of Respondents (n=134)

Figure 1 displays the overall distribution of the participants according to their optimism level. The optimism level with the highest number of respondents is under the low optimism level. This implies that more than half of the selected ABM 12 students are low in optimism. The lowest distribution is found among the students who scored along the range of high optimism level, only three (3) or 2% of the respondents were recorded to be highly optimistic. Overall, the results show that most of the participants are lowly optimistic which contrasts with other studies (Adams, 2013, as cited in Wood, 2020; Ipsos, 2018).

Figure 1.1 Score Distribution under Low Optimism Level

In Figure 1.1, specific scores individuals garnered under the low optimism level are shown. The highest distribution is those who scored 13 and 12 on the LOT-R with twenty-eight (28) respondents, respectively. This implies that more than half (69%) of the students who scored under low optimism are near to having moderate optimism. The lowest distribution is those who answered under the score of 9 and are considered as others. The scores under Others, which only had one (1) respondent each, are 3, 6, 7, and 8. Thus, the highest score under low optimism is 13 with twenty-eight (28) respondents, while the lowest score was 3 with only one (1) participant who got it.

Figure 1.3 Score Distribution under High Optimism Level

Figure 1.3 presents the score distribution under high optimism level. It was found that only three (3) participants got a score of 19 which is the lowest for the high optimism level which ranges from 19-24. This shows that out of all the one hundred thirty-four (134) participants, only less than 3% got a score under high optimism. It may also imply that the Grade 12 ABM students of Lourdes College, Inc. are more pessimistic than optimistic. Luepker (2015) states optimism is important for individuals, especially those who aspire to become entrepreneurs, in the future because it will help them to create solutions, and opportunities.

Figure 1.2 Score Distribution under Moderate Optimism Level

Figure 1.2 shows the specific scores under Moderate Optimism level and the following number of participants who got the scores. The score that got the highest distribution of participants is 15, which has sixteen (16) respondents while the score that got the lowest distribution is 17 and 18 which has five (5) respondents each. Moreover, there are fifteen (15) participants that scored 14 which may support the implication. It is explained that it is important for an individual to find the middle (moderate) between optimism and pessimism which is considered as the desirable optimum (Hecht, 2013) suggesting that having moderate optimism is better however, empirical studies have indicated that having more optimism rather than being in the optimum has more advantages regarding one's general attitude or outlook in life (Supervia et al., 2020, as cited in Piper, 2019).

Table 1 Overall Average Degree of Optimism

LOT-R Scores (LS)	Number of Respondents (NR)	LS(NR) = Total	Verbal Description (LOT-R)
3	1	3	Low Optimism
6	1	6	Low Optimism
7	1	7	Low Optimism
8	1	8	Low Optimism
9	5	45	Low Optimism
10	3	30	Low Optimism
11	13	143	Low Optimism
12	28	336	Low Optimism
13	28	364	Low Optimism
14	15	210	Moderate Optimism
15	16	240	Moderate Optimism
16	9	144	Moderate Optimism
17	5	85	Moderate Optimism
18	5	90	Moderate Optimism
19	3	57	High Optimism
Overall Average Score		13.2≈13	Low Optimism

For the first research question, the Table 1.4 shows that the participants are lowly optimistic. Out of all the possible scores to obtain from the LOT-R, most of the respondents scored under 12 and 13 which have twenty-eight (28) students each. The score that got the second highest distribution is sixteen (16) which is under the score of 15. It is implied that the selected students of the Grade 12 ABM have somewhat a negative outlook in life (Chowdhury, 2020).

Although the score is under low optimism, it may also suggest that the students are near to being moderately optimistic. In contrast to optimism, the study of Lang et al. (2013) suggests that individuals who were found to be overly optimistic about their future had a correlation with higher risks of death and disability. They also stated that pessimism may encourage other persons to take care of their life carefully regarding health and safety. Furthermore, Riveiro's (2014) study found that a higher number of students utilized optimistic strategies than pessimistic however; a positive relationship between the two (2) strategies exists in terms of motivation and results. This suggests that even though students may be pessimistic, they can still use this mindset in order to strategize on dealing with challenges.

Research Question 2: What is the level of entrepreneurial skill of the respondents in terms of team effectiveness?

Figure 2 Average Team Effectiveness Score of Participants per Optimism Level

Figure 2 shows the average team effectiveness scores of the participants according to their respective optimism levels. The highest average, of 38, comes from the participants who scored under high optimism level. Accordingly, the average team effectiveness score descends on the following levels which may imply that the higher the optimism level, the higher the team effectiveness skill, and vice versa. The lowest average score is 31.3 and was garnered by the respondents who scored under low optimism level. The findings support previous studies that have shown the relationship between team effectiveness skill and optimism (Achor & Gielan, 2020, as cited in Niyogi, 2017; Kenneally, 2015).

Figure 2.1 presents the average scores on each aspect of team effectiveness skill obtained by the respondents who are under low optimism level. It shows that the Roles and Team Relationships aspect have the highest mean score of 4.1. On the other hand, the aspects of Team Processes, Intergroup Relations, Problem Solving, and Passion and Commitment have a mean score of 3.8, which is the lowest average among all. This implies that the participants have difficulty when it comes solving issues (Oliveri et al., 2017) in the team; they also have issues regarding team processes which deal with how the participants are able to integrate their capabilities in order to accomplish common goals (Crawford, 2020); they also lack passion and commitment which suggest that they are not willing and determined to work (Stoia, 2018); and they also lack when it comes to helping and interacting with other groups, if present (Kramer & Schaffer, 2015).

Figure 2.1 Mean Scores for Each Aspect of Team Effectiveness per Optimism Level

Figure 2.1 also displays the participants who scored under moderate optimism levels have high mean scores for the Roles and Team Relationship aspects, the same as those respondents who scored under low optimism. However, the aspect with the least mean score is Intergroup Relations. The results suggest that the participants under moderate optimism levels, same as with low optimism, are good at knowing their roles and responsibilities in the group as well as have good relationships with their co-members. The second highest mean score is 4.2 from Purpose and Goals meaning that second to Roles and Team Relationship, participants are also good at knowing their group's intention like what is the group aiming to achieve. Relative to the participants who have low optimism, the respondents under this level also have difficulty with intergroup relations which imply that they have trouble with interacting with other groups.

The results show that participants who scored under high optimism levels got a perfect mean score of 5 under the aspects of Roles and Problem Solving. This implies that the participants know perfectly their roles and responsibilities when being put in a group (Vodopivec & Hmelak, 2015), and that when there are problems encountered, they are proactive and are able to present solutions that can help overcome the situation (Raison et al., 2015). However, the participants only scored a mean of 4.5 under Passion and Commitment. Although a score of 4.5 is not that small, it also suggests that the participants have lesser focus on passion and committing to their work but in comparison to other optimism levels, not one of each aspect in low and moderate levels reached a mean score of 4.5.

Table 2 Overall Average Score of Participants on Team Effectiveness and its Impact

Aspects of Team Effectiveness	Overall Average Score
Purpose and Goals	4.10
Roles	4.17
Team Processes	3.90
Team Relationships	4.19
Intergroup Relations	3.85
Problem Solving	3.92
Passion and Commitment	3.87
Skills and Learning	4.06
Overall Average Team Effectiveness Score	32.06

Table 2.2 shows that the selected Grade 12 ABM students have an overall average team effectiveness score of 32.06. The highest possible score is 40 which imply that 32.06 is already a good enough score to consider that the students are team effective. The highest aspect is Team Relationships in which it implies that the participants are good in communicating with their co-members and are able to establish good bond between them as well. The second highest aspect is Roles which has an overall average score of 4.17, which suggests that the participants easily know what to do when situated in a group work. Furthermore, the aspect with the lowest average score is Intergroup Relations which suggests that the participants have difficulty in creating a bond or cooperating with other groups.

Research Question 3: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents’ optimism level towards their team effectiveness skill as well as its aspects?

Table 3.1 displays the Spearman’s Correlation Coefficient of each pair of independent and dependent variables. The p value was determined using a post hoc t-test while the Spearman rho was manually calculated. All of the pairs have a significant relationship with each other, albeit weak. A weak correlation implies the possibility of the independent variable to have a relationship with the dependent variables however, it cannot be overlooked that even if it is a weak correlation, it is still a significant positive correlation.

For the overall team effectiveness skill, the p value is 0.0011 which is below the alpha of 0.05 implying that the findings are statistically significant to reject the null hypothesis. The results, which show that optimism correlates with team effective, coincide with previous studies (Caprara et al., 2015, as cited in Hsu & Wang, 2012). Out of the eight (8) aspects of team effectiveness skill, only one, Intergroup Relations, failed to prove its relationship towards optimism. Intergroup Relations also had the lowest Spearman rho which was 0.1338 which is almost near to having no relationship. Nevertheless, the other seven (7) aspects of team effectiveness, although having a positive weak correlation, were able to prove the significance of the correlation such that their null hypotheses are rejected. It is also worth noting that the Spearman rho is highest with Team Relationships and second to Roles.

Table 3 Value of Spearman’s Correlation Coefficient and P value

Independent and Dependent Variable	Spearman Rho	P value (α = 0.05)	Interpretation
1) Optimism and Purpose and Goals	0.2521	.0033	Reject
2) Optimism and Roles	0.2919	.0006	Reject
3) Optimism and Team Processes	0.2826	.0009	Reject
4) Optimism and Team Relationships	0.3525	.0000	Reject
5) Optimism and Intergroup Relations	0.1338	.1232	Fail to reject
6) Optimism and Problem Solving	0.2020	.0193	Reject
7) Optimism and Passion and Commitment	0.2833	.0009	Reject
8) Optimism and Skills and Learning	0.2482	.0038	Reject
9) Optimism and Team Effectiveness Skill	0.2781	.0011	Reject

Conclusions and Recommendations

The optimism levels of the participants contrast the findings of previous studies of Adams (2013) and Wood (2020). Other studies have also shown the importance of optimism in teenagers such that it will be beneficial for them in the future such as academic success, better physical and mental health, and overall outlook in life (Shaheen, 2015, as cited in Duraku & Hoxha, 2018; Mishra, 2012). There is also the possibility of optimism factors such as family (Cook, 2014, as cited in McHale et al., 2012), friends (Albert et al., 2013, as cited in Kacperczyk, 2013), and current situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic, wherein Eva et al. (2020) has stated that people tend to be more pessimistic during the pandemic because of the sudden upcoming of the virus and its effects on the welfare of the society, are what makes the participants have that particular optimism level.

The team effectiveness skill of the respondents bears a similarity towards their optimism levels. Participants have a difficulty regarding their Passion and Commitment, a study shows that there is a relationship between optimism and passion such that individuals who are more optimistic tend to be more passionate about their work, and individuals who were more pessimistic tend to be less passionate (Hansen et al., 2014). Another aspect the participants were lacking in is Intergroup Relations, Smith et al. (2016) have found in their study that optimism and pessimism levels of individuals affect their interpersonal and/or social skills which give an implication that low optimism relates with trouble regarding intergroup relations which require interpersonal and/or social skills. It can also be that the current situation such as the pandemic have affected the respondents' team effectiveness skill such that, according to Kniffin et al. (2020), the virtual setting may have an implication on the performance losses of individuals during the pandemic because of doing team tasks only online in which communication and cooperation is a challenge.

Findings regarding the relationship between optimism and Intergroup Relations show that there is not sufficient evidence to prove its relationship thus, the null hypothesis was failed to reject. Nonetheless, the participants' degree of optimism and overall team effectiveness skill, as well as the other seven (7) aspects, resulted to a positive significant relationship indicating that such relationship does exist therefore, the null hypothesis of the following relationships were rejected. It is also found that most of the variables have a weak positive correlation but it cannot be overlooked that it is a significant positive relationship. The researchers conclude that there truly is a significant relationship between the respondents' degree of optimism and team effectiveness skill (Bi-fen & Mei-ling, 2012, as cited in Niyogi, 2017; Kenneally, 2015). During the pandemic, it has been stated in the previous conclusions that it affects both the optimism and team effectiveness of individuals. Individuals who have stronger optimism tend to be more coping with the current crisis (Bransford et al., 2020) but may have low or high team effectiveness (Mayo, 2020), while lower optimism levels may have low or high team effectiveness. The researchers also conclude that present environmental factors may also have an implication on the relationship of the independent and dependent variables.

With the findings of this study, the researchers recommend the following:

For students, regardless of the course or strand taken, it is inevitable that students will face group work, not only in school, but also in the future when they will have jobs. With the results found in this study, students are recommended to develop their optimism as it will have an affect or influence towards the productivity of their team. The researchers also recommend that the students will learn about team effectiveness such that they will be able of value to the group and will be able to contribute to do the work. For school administrations, to give considerations in creating and implementing strategies that can further develop the students' optimism as well as team effectiveness skill.

For future researchers, they are recommended to find the gaps in this study and answer them as well. The scope of the study is only limited to Grade 12 ABM students so the researchers highly recommend that future researchers will venture out to more areas like making a study with Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students, or Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students, or even Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) students. Furthermore, the study did not include gender difference so it is highly suggested that it should be considered for future studies as well. There are also factors in the independent variable that are not included in the study, so it is a recommendation for the future researchers to identify more about the factors of optimism and their relationship towards the team effectiveness of students. The results of the study also show that there is no significant relationship between optimism and Intergroup Relations, thus research regarding this topic are highly recommended. The researchers also recommend looking deeper within each aspect of team effectiveness skill and investigate probable causes of the development of each aspect. Lastly, further research is suggested to determine the causes of the weak positive relationship between the variables as well as the specific effects of optimism towards the team effectiveness skill.

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